

**L1 INPUT IN L2 OUTPUT WORD FOR WORD TRANSLATION:
A CRITICAL CONTRASTIVE STUDY OF MORPHO-SYNTAX OF
INVERSION IN DIRECT REPORTED SPEECH IN GEORGE ORWELL
ENGLISH AND FRENCH ANIMAL FARM CORPUS**

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Abstract:

In 21st Century, Translation has been one of very important field in multicultural communication. Though disparities of thoughts in the point of views of some scholars with different oriented paradigms either translation should be word for word, literal, syntactic, semantic or pragmatic. Chomsky extrapolation theory of direct translation of X transfer to Y, Peter Newmark “sense for sense”, Cisero “free translation», *L1 in L2*, *Krashen* (1981), Jacobson etc. The scientific debates engaged by the previous cited scholars have never settled the problems of similarities and differences that may still exist between a pair of languages. Thus, translation of SL (source language) into TL (language) should not only limit at word for word, L1 & L2 input-output hypothesis, but also should understand **accuracy, meaning, context, and audience**. While the problem of translation method and application to meet equivalence is still a dilemma to some teachers and scholars, novice and practitioners when prior involving in translation and lacking faithfulness of SL & TL in South –Kivu institutions of higher education (DRC), the work has enriched the debate by suggesting to the translator how to frame his translation duty not only prior engaging into water sinking and diving without being familiarized with the context of water diving but also should encounter both the rules governing the feature of L1 morphological construction either applicable or non-applicable to L2 morphological construction.

The paper raises a question: does the rule of L1 morphological construction generalization of (UG) universal grammar serve in the production of L2 construction of inversion in direct reported speech? To answer to this question ,the study consisted of collecting data from two novels George Orwell *Animal Farm* and *La Ferme d’animaux*; English-French Translated corpus to understand linguistic phenomena that may still exist between a pair of languages in translation.

The present paper has applied qualitative method grounding contrastive analysis in the processing of the data. The finding reveals that similarities and differences can still exist

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between a pair of language. This means that it is so that (L a) because in L1 there is a rule A that is crucially involved in the derivation of structure of type X having the property of α , where in L2 there is a corresponding rule B that is involved in the same way in the derivation of structures of the type Y which differ from X having the property β where the former had α . So, any attempt to faithfully translate SL into TL requires the mastery of rules governing the linguistic features of both L1 & L2 which might occur similar or different while targeting accuracy, meaning, context and audience perception.

Keywords: L1 & L2 Input-Output, word-for-word, morho-syntax, inversion, accuracy, meaning, context, audience

1. Introduction

Translation is the communicative meaning of a source language text by means of equivalent target –language text. The English language draws a terminology distinction (not all languages do) between translating a written text and interpreting (oral or sign –language communication between users of different languages). Under this distinction, translation can begin only after the appearance of writing within a language community. Discussions of theory and practice of translation reach back into antiquity and show remarkable continuities. The ancient Greek distinguished between metaphrase (Literal translation) and paraphrase. This distinction was adopted by English poet and translator John Dryden (1631-1700) who described translation as the judicious blending of these two modes of phrasing when selecting in the target language, "counterparts «or equivalents, for the expressions used in the source language. This general formulation of the central concept of translation – equivalence is as adequate as any that has been proposed since Cicero and Horace, who, in 1st Century-BC Rome, famously and literally cautioned against translating "word for word" *verbum pro verbo*. Later Chomsky challenged the theory with (UG) universal Grammar with L1 morphological construction as a rule serving for the production of any L2 language (ξ :Sentence ,F: $X_1 -Y_1 ,X_n -Y_n$).Chomsky'(UG) has been applied by many scholars in 21st C when prior engaging in the translation of SL into TL. (UG) of Chomsky's theory of L1 & L2 construction ($X_1 =Y_1$), *L1 in L2, Krashen* and Terrell (1983: 41–42) has been observed as a construction of direct word –for- word translation which still encounters problems of equivalence to many scholars in South-Kivu institutions of higher education (DRC) when prior engaging in the translation of SL to TL.

The present paper has applied qualitative method grounding contrastive analysis to fruitfully help us understand similarities and differences that can still exist between a pair of language. As finding, the present study has mainly focused on morpho-syntax analysis of inversion in direct reported speech in English and French *Animal Farm* translated corpus to help the audience and mainly translators in South-Kivu(DRC) understand cross-linguistic argumentation with a focus on the construction of linguistic theory of UG($X_1 =Y_1$) as not to be considered as consisting entirely of inductive generalization of what is to be found within the

grammars of any particular languages. Any attempt to translate SL in TL requires on one hand, the mastery of rules governing linguistic features of both L1 & L2, on the other hand, targeting accuracy, meaning, context and audience to meet equivalence.

2. Discussion

Following the investigation along with the following axes, F1 & F2 lead a critic translator to involve into questions and issues:

- Does X₁-Y₁ direct translation meet equivalence?
- Does word for word meet accuracy?
- Does L₁ Input to L₂ Output hypothesis direct translation meet context and audience perception?

To answer to these questions two alternatives are possible for a critic translator to confront these issues. First, L1 transfer can have some effects on L2 in some areas which cannot be extrapolated by a translator as inductive generalization of what is to be found in grammars of any particular languages. However, Word for word translation may still lead to gaps in some generalization cases of language syntax and semantic transability. Second, if we are to understand by the term transverbalization from one language into another, particularly from English to French vice-versa. That will push to syntactical and semantical investigation. There are some operational syntaxes, whose elaboration will vary according to context and audience as stated by Victor A. Oswald, Jr. To understand these issues of similarities and differences among a pair of languages let us examine these possible cases of L1 input & L2 output in morpho-syntax of inversion from *Animal Farm* English-French translated corpus see:

Table 1. Similarities and differences in morpho-syntax of direct reported speech English-French translated corpus

A	English Corpus George Orwell " <i>Animal Farm</i> "	B	French Corpus George Orwell « <i>La Ferme d'animaux</i> »
1(a)	X ₁ "Comrades" he said , "I have a point that must be settled "	1(b)	Y ₁ "Camarades", dit-il , "il ya une question à trancher »
2(a)	X ₁ « Mollie », She said « I have something very serious to say to you »	2(b)	Y ₁ "Camarades", dit-elle , "il ya une question à trancher".
3(a)	X ₁ « No », Said Snowball firmly « We have no means of making sugar on this farm	3(b)	Y ₁ "Non" déclara Boule de Neige fermement. "Nous n'avons aucun moyen de faire du sucre sur cette ferme ».
4(a)	X ₁ « And shall I still be allowed to wear ribbons in my name?" Asked Mollie .	4(b)	Y ₁ "Et devrais-je encore porter des rubans dans ma crinière ? » demanda Lubie
5(a)	X ₁ « Comrades », said Snowball , It is half-past six and we have a long day before us."	5(b)	Y ₁ "Camarades», dit Boule de Neige , «Il est six heures et demie et nous avons une longue journée avant nous. »
6(a)	X ₁ « Ribbons, » he said , Should be considered as clothes, which are the mark of human being.	6(b)	Y ₁ "Les Rubans", dit-il « devraient être considérés comme des vêtements ,qui ont la marque d'un être humain.

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7(a)	X ₁ « Now Comrades » <u>Cried Snowball</u> , throwing down the point brush, to the hayfield!	7(b)	Y ₁ « Et maintenant, camarades, aux foins ! » <u>Se cria Boule de Neige.</u>
8(a)	X ₁ « What is going to happen to all that milk? ” <u>Said some one.</u>	8(b)	Y ₁ « Qu’est ce qui va arriver à tout ce lait ? » <u>dit quelqu’un.</u>
9(a)	X ₁ “Jones used sometimes to mix some of it in our mash” <u>Said one of the hens.</u>	9(b)	Y ₁ Jones parfois mélangeait un peu de cela dans notre purée », <u>déclara l’une des poules</u>
10(a)	X ₁ « Comrades », <u>he said,</u> “I trust that every animal here appreciates the sacrifice that Comrade Napoleon made in taking this extra labor upon himself.	10(b)	Y ₁ “Camarades” <u>dit-il,</u> j’espère que tous les animaux ici apprécient le sacrifice que Camarade Napoléon a fait en prenant ce travail supplémentaire sur lui-même.

In the sentences above , the shift word order between English and French direct reported clause presents some similarities where by inverted subject –verb order is inevitable in both English and French languages when the subject is a nominal as viewed 3(a), 3(b), 4(b), 5(a), 5(b), 7(a), 7(b), 8(a), 8(b) from illustrated examples above. A derivational hypothesis of inverted subject verb order in reported direct speech is postulated for English to account for phenomenon together with convincing evidence taken when a reporting clause has a nominal subject in both English and French so, the inversion is inevitable. Thus, L1 & L2 or X₁-Y₁ sentence structure direct morphological construction rule is applicable.

However, following the investigation along with the table above, there are two arguments in which the data above can be fruitfully and uncontroversial appealed to. First, as we may see in the examples of English–French translated corpus above: 1(a), 1(b), 2(a), 2(b), 6(a), 6(b), 10(a), 10(b).It is observable that English and French direct reported speech reveal a slight difference in the construction of morphological syntax of subject-verb. In English corpus, direct reporting clause as represented above in: 1(a), 2(a), 6(a), 10(a) presents the impossibility of inverted subject-verb when the subject is a pronoun. Thus, non-direct applicability of L1 & L2 or X₁-X₂ word for word construction as a consequence leads to ungrammaticality of the sentence. In this case, English and French reveal a slight difference in the construction of morphological syntax of direct reported clause (subject-verb);in English direct reporting clause as represented in: 1(a), 2(a), 6(a), 10(a) reveals the impossibility of inverted subject – verb when the subject is a pronoun. Whereas in French morphological syntax construction of 1(b), 2(b), 6(b), 10(b) reporting clause see **Table 1**, the inverted subject-verb is obligatory. However, French-English translated corpuses following word-to word canonical order tends to be ungrammatical see the Table 2 French-English inverted order:

Table 2: French-English Word-for-word or X₁-Y₁ leading to ungrammatical translation

A	French Corpus	B	English Corpus: Word-for-word (Ungrammatical) Translation
1.(a)	X ₁ “Camarades”, <u>dit-il</u> ,“il ya une question à trancher	1.(b)	Y ₁ « Comrades », <u>Said-he</u> , Here is a point that must be settled.
2.(a)	X ₁ “Lubie”, <u>dit-elle</u> ,“j’ai à te parler tout à fait sérieusement”.	2.(b)	Y ₁ « Mollie », <u>Said-she</u> , “I have something very serious to say to you”.
6.(a)	X ₁ “Les Rubans”, <u>dit-il</u> ,« devraient être considérés comme des vêtements, qui ont la	6.(b)	Y ₁ « Ribbons, » <u>Said-he</u> , Should be considered as clothes ,which are the mark of human being

<p>marque d'un être humain ».</p> <p>10.(a) X₁ "Camarades" dit-il, j'espère que tous les animaux ici apprécient le sacrifice que Camarade Napoléon a fait en prenant ce travail supplémentaire sur lui-même</p>	<p>10.(b) Y₁ « Comrades », Said-he, "I trust that every animal here appreciates the sacrifice that Comrade Napoleon made in taking this extra labor upon himself".</p>
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In the exploratory of the sentences above, the rules governing the structure of French and English direct reported speech tend to be different; which would require attributed semantic and syntactic construction knowledge of the parallel sentences.

In French, the sentences which begin with direct quotation following by a reporting clause constitute a particular case of inversion see Table 2 1(a), 2(a), 6(a), 10(a). However, English does not, the impossibility and ungrammaticality of inverted subject verb in English occur when a clitic subject character is a pronoun see **table 2** above: 1(b), 2(b), 6(b), 10(b).

For French in reported direct speech, Inversion applies both a clitic and non clitic subject, its place is always after the finite verb in reported direct speech. If the subject is non clitic, it must be placed after the whole verb phrase. English applies the same rule on condition that the subject is nominal see **Table 1**: 3(a), 3(b), 4(a), 4(b), 5(a), 5(b), 7(a), 7(b), 8(a), 8(b). Here in this context, L1 to L2 inversion word order from Source Language (SL) to Target Language (TL) direct construction or X₁-Y₁ direct morphological construction is possible in both English and French when non clitic subject is **nominal** in both French and English, but in both French and English up to now, when the clitic subject is a pronoun would lead to focus on the syntactic and semantic conditions that must be fulfilled in order to make inversion possible or impossible from SL to TL, here each language applies its own rules. French applies inversion for both clitic and non clitic subject where as English in direct reported speech does not, any attempt to apply inversion when the clitic subject is pronoun leads to ungrammaticality. So, for English rule no inversion in direct reported speech when a clitic subject is a pronoun. At this stage, we have to pay attention to the consequences for the grammaticality of the sentence following from the application or lack of application of the rule. One of the main differences between English and French vice-versa with regard to word order is the fact that, in English & French, inversion is generally felt as a structure which belongs to careful language style and not to familiar word for word conversational situation Hulk (1994).

Figure 1: Translation Research questioning and analyzing and hypothesizing

Considering the investigation along with any one among these axes leads to a critic translator to involve into questions and issues about clusters L1(SL) to L1(TL), Accuracy, Meaning, Context, and Audience. It is possible if the translator can recognize the patterns of syntactic connection, or can establish the significance of meaning bearing words to meet both context and audience, the task that unfortunately our poor machines or novice translators are incapable of performing. The problem of translation of block by block word for word would lead in some areas to gaps in terms of equivalence. Syntactic connection will almost infallibly identify word-function that can be built into “memory” of the translator or machines of the high speed computer type. Word-by-word regardless accuracy, meaning, context, and audience in some areas lead to ungrammaticality resulting into audience’s readability ambiguity or confusion.

Nida argues on ideas concerning dynamic equivalence, on meaning and the target audience. The L1 rules should not be seen as something self-governing dependent L2 construction. The context plays as well a crucial role when discussing equivalence matters, the later involves when discussing translation as action, since “each cultural domain, each cultural language, has its historicity (Meschonnic 2003,342). When considering functional equivalence issues the aim is accordingly to Hjørland’s (1997) ideas about functional equivalence to also take into account what is reasonable to link and compare. In order to place a functionally equivalent TL text beside a SL text, the translator should clarify the functions of the SL text. This may be carried out either by starting from the smallest textual unit and ending with the analysis of the smallest unit. This means that after analyzing the

functions of the text, the text type and text variety, produces the phrase of reverbalsation. This can be understood as such the text type determines the general method for translating as well as the text type variety demands consideration for language, and text structure convention". (Ibid, 166).

To overcome the problems of word by word (X_1 - Y_1) direct translation, New mark (Ibid,47) advocates that semantic and communicative translation fulfill the two aims of translation which are first, accuracy and economy. According to Newmark (1998), Communicative translation attempts to render the exact contextual meaning of the original in such a way that both content and language are readily acceptable and comprehensible to readership. Competence based translation views a translator as often seen as compatriot of the TL audience rather than the SL author, which means that the translator and audience should share the same cultural and national background. This bridge between the translator and his audience is cultural linguistic. So, translation should not only limit at word-for-word but also requires looking at accuracy, meaning, cultural context, audience which are elements beyond L1 input to L2 output direct translation. Since each language has got its own syntactic, semantic and pragmatic rules governing features of language structure. So, the process of translation should often be hindered by structural, lexical and contextual constraints. Lindfors (2001,6) argues that translation is not a value free-action and choices are made at all the stages of the process ;what to translate, to whom, how etc. Thus, the translator should be familiarized with both SL and TL in order to meet competence based translation.

3. Conclusion

The present study investigated on L1 input to L2 output word for word translation (X_1 - Y_1) theory as a critical analysis of morpho-syntax inversion in direct reported speech English-French translated corpus. Though disparities in the view points of some scholars: Chomsky (UG) with X_1 - Y_1 direct translation, Krashen L1 in L2, Cisero, Peternewmark, Nida, Jakobson etc, the work has raised questions: Does X_1 - Y_1 direct translation meet equivalence? Does the generalization of L1 (SL) morphological construction rules serve obligatorily as a model of L2 (TL) construction? Does L1 in L2 direct translation meet context and audience perception? To answer to these questions, the work has applied qualitative method grounding contrastive analysis of morpho-syntax inversion in direct reported clause to help the audience understand the similarities and differences that may still exist between a pair of languages, especially to some teachers, scholars, novice and professional translators in South-Kivu (DRC), where difficulties are still much observable in the field of translation.

As finding, the work has revealed that any attempt to transfer SL (Source Language) into TL (Target language) requires the understanding of rules (syntactic, semantic, pragmatic and stylistic) governing X_1 feature of L1 and Y_1 feature of L2 either similar or different, applicable or not applicable. So, the translator should not only limit at the linguistic theory of word-for word, but also have a ground understanding of accuracy, meaning, context, audience to meet the equivalence.

Bibliography

1. Baker, Mona (1992). Course book on translation. London: Routledge
2. Catford, John C. (1965). A Linguistic Theory of Translation: An essay on Applied Linguistics, London: Oxford University Press.
3. Cicero, Horace (1st C.B.C). Free translation
4. Ferguson, Charles A. (1968). Contrastive analysis and language development. Washington D.C.: George Town Univ. Press
5. Fisiak, Jacek, ed. (1973). Papers and studies in contrastive linguistics. Vol 1. Poznan: Adam Mickiewicz Univ. Press
6. George Orwell (1947). *Animal Farm, La Ferme d'Animaux*
7. HJorland's (1997). The Foundation of concept of relevance
8. Jakobson, Roman (1959). On Linguistic Aspect of Translation," R. A. Brower (ed) On Translation Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.pp.232-39
9. Korzen (1992:113 f).Language at synchronicity
10. Krashen, S. D. (1981). The Input hypothesis: Issues and Implications: New york, Longman
11. Lindfors (2001, 6). The theory and Practice in Language
12. Meschonnic (2003, 342). Ethics and Politics of Translating
13. Newmark (1998). A Text book of Translation.Amazon.com
14. Nida, Eugene A. and C. R. Taber (1969/1982). The Theory and Practice of Translation
15. Noam Chomsky (1985). Universal Grammar and Second Language Learning, Volume 6, Issue1, Oxford University Press

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